

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CONCRETE COLUMNS COATED BY COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH DIFFERENT STAKING SEQUENCES

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SUMMARY

We describe a study undertaken on a series of columns reinforced by composite materials glass/polyester with several lay ups under uniaxial compression loading. The reinforced columns show an increase up to 70% in rigidity and failure load compared with non-reinforced ones, when only two plies of composite material are used.

Keywords: Concrete column, Compression, wrapped columns, composite Materials, fibres orientations.

INTRODUCTION

Techniques based on repair and re-qualification of reinforced concrete structures using composite materials have showed so far excellent performances [1], due to the many advantages provided by composite materials. The structural updating techniques are currently extended to various types of structures, like reinforced concrete columns for seismic and corrosive environments [2], beams [3], flagstones [4] and walls veils [5]. Moreover, the degradation of civil engineering structure materials, like the corrosion of reinforcing steels, is often the primary reason for insufficient structural capacity. Ilki and Kumbasar [6] tested both damaged and undamaged cylinder specimens, which were externally confined with different thickness of CFRP jackets, under monotonic increasing and cyclic compressive stresses. Based on experimental results they proposed some simple expressions for ultimate strength and corresponding axial strain of CFRP jacketed concrete. Ilki et al. [7] tested also specimens with longitudinal and transverse reinforcement and different cross-section shapes were under uniaxial compression. Six of the specimens with different cross-sectional shapes were constructed using low strength concrete to investigate the effects of concrete quality. For simulating the columns of the existing structures, particularly in developing countries, plain reinforcement. Extensive experimental data for cylinder specimens, for a variety of fibre types, orientations and jacket thickness, either for FRP jacketed concrete or concrete filled FRP tubes was developed in the literature [8-13]. Recently, Tamuzs et al. [14] studied the stability and strength of concrete columns confined by circumferential wrappings and strengthened with a longitudinal external CFRP reinforcement.

At the present time, the need to provide repairs to concrete reinforcement is very important, and the use of composite materials for this application is very promising for

future constructions. In this work a series of concrete columns are subjected to uniaxial compression loading. The tests are performed on concrete columns alone and on wrapped with a jacket composite laminate one. The aim of this paper is to highlight the influence of the fibre orientations, the thickness of the composite jackets and the fibre types (tissue, mat and hybrid) on the failure load and the damage mechanisms which result from it.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Specimen preparations

The concrete columns are prepared by batches of 50 components by a company having a concrete batching and mixing plant. The columns have standard size (16 cm diameter, 32 cm height), with fairly uniform values of the cross-section and length distributions. They are submitted for testing of compression 28 days after casting. In this study three types of reinforcements were used in order to reinforce by coating the concrete columns. The first and the second reinforcement are glass E bidirectional tissue which a surface density of 500 g/m², and 300 g/m², and the third reinforcement is a mat which a surface density of 300 g/m². The columns are coated by two composite layers (glass/polyester) with an average thickness of 0.83 mm each one.

Wrapped concrete columns

The technique employed to wrap the columns by FRP is the ROCC process (Reinforcement Overages Composite Coated). This technique (also called direct stratification or polymerization in-situ) consists applying a layer of resin to the surface of the concrete column and a following tissue of glass having 320 mm length E by 505 mm of width as reinforcements. An additional length of 250 mm is used in the direction of circle to provide an overlapping. A brush is used to help to wrap tissue and at the end another layer of resin was applied to the top of tissue. This achieved a coated layer of composite FRP and the process was repeated to apply the subsequent layers. The main advantage of the reinforcement by dry tissues is the easy handling on building site, with a complete absence of heavy material to move. This technique allows in particular a perfect follow-up of the shape of the structure to be reinforced.

In this study, a first series of columns were wrapped using five fibre orientations in order to investigate the effect of the composite lay-up on the structural behaviours of the concrete columns wrapped by FRP. A second series of columns were reinforced by employing various types of reinforcements: bidirectional tissues E-glass with a surface density of 500 g/m² and 300 g/m², a mat, and hybrid with a number of layers varying from 1 to 4 layers. This investigation leads to highlight the effect of the reinforcement type and thickness of FRP on the behaviour of the coated concrete columns.

Testing

The concrete columns reinforced by FRP were subjected to uniaxial monotonous compression loading until the failure of FRP. The tests were carried out at the laboratory of Civil Engineering and Hydraulics (LGCH of university of Guelma). The machine used is a hydraulic press 'CONTROLS_Model 50-C55G2/L' whose capacity is of 3000 kN. The higher plate is mobile in rotation of such kind to marry the surface of the specimens. The vertical effort is applied gradually via the lower plate, with a constant rate loading until the failure of the specimens. Machine stops is not automatic,

when the maximum force is reached posting stops and the machine is stopped. The DIGIMAX PLUS directly posts the load/time curve in parallel with the test, and the data acquisition system linked to the computer can directly record the data on a file.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FRP preparation specimens and tensile testing

In order to determine the properties of the FRP, specimens were prepared using the same raw materials. All the laminate plates have three bidirectional plies, with dimensions 20 mm of width, 250 mm length and 2 mm thickness. Each end of the specimens was tabbed using 20 mm wide by 38 mm long aluminum tabs with a gauge length of 174 mm. Tow lay-ups were used to prepare the specimens: $(0/90)_3$, and $(\pm 45)_3$ from the axial loading direction. The samples were tested using a Zwik machine with the capacity of 100 kN to determine their tensile strength using **ASTM D 3171** standard. Figure 1, show the load/displacement behaviour of the polyester resin specimens and the composite lay-ups $(\pm 45)_3$, $(0/90)_3$ associated to there failure modes.

Figure 1 a) Load/displacement behaviour of a polyester resin compared to the composite laminate with a lay-ups $(0/90)_3$, $(\pm 45)_3$ with there rupture modes b) and c) respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fibre orientation influence on the wrapped concrete columns

Figure 2 shows the time history of the load for the wrapped columns with different lay-ups, compared to the one of the control concrete which occurs on three phase's. The first nonlinear phase corresponding to small force values does not involve the formation of cracks in the concrete, therefore the columns behave elastically. During the second phase, cracking along the vertical direction induces an increase in longitudinal deflection and lower stiffness, providing therefore another significant linear behaviour with a different slope. It can be noticed that the higher rigidity is obtained for the specimens coated by $(0/90)_2$ and with the augmentation of the angle from 0 to 20 for the lay-up $(+20/-70)_2$ the rigidity became slightly dawn but steel higher than the concrete control and the minimum is obtained for $(+30/-60)_2$. However, for the staking sequences with angle higher than 30 degrees an increase of the rigidity is notice for the lay-ups $(+40/-50)_2$ and $(+50/-40)_2$ but steel lower than the concrete control. Finally, the third

phase corresponds to the behaviour of the composite jacket recovering the concrete columns. The curves take the same form, apart from the case related to the behaviour of the column reinforced by the composite lay-up $(0/90)_2$. From these results it appears that two lay ups provide the most interesting performances; the laminates $(0/90)_2$ and $(+30/-60)_2$. The maximum load at failure is obtained for the lay up $(+30/-60)_2$ providing an increase of 70% compared to the concrete control (Table 1). It is important to notice also that the damage mechanisms of the columns depend strongly on the fibre orientations, as represented in figure 2.

Figure 2 Load/time curves of the columns coated by various lay-ups compared to the concrete control.

Tableau 1 Strengthening efficiency of wrapped concrete columns.

Fibre orientations	$(0/90)_2$	$(+50/-40)_2$	$(+40/-50)_2$	$(+30/-60)_2$	$(+20/-70)_2$	Concrete control
Average Load (kN)	847.2	814.3	843.5	910.5	864.1	537.8

Failure modes

Figure 3 shows some typical damage modes of various lay-ups of FRP wrapping the concrete columns, together with the pure concrete control specimen. For the fibres oriented at $(+20/-70)_2$, $(+30/-60)_2$, $(+40/-50)_2$, and $(-50/+40)_2$, the crack propagates along the fibre direction. However, for the lay-up $(0/90)_2$ the crack propagation is perpendicular to the fibre direction. This type of failure mode can be also explained by the change of the longitudinal tensile stress, transverse tensile stress, and in-plan shear stress with fibre orientations.

Figure 3. Typical damage modes of concrete control and various lay-ups of FRP wrapped concrete columns. a) Concrete control b), c) and d) various lay-ups of FRP $(0/90)_2$, $(+30/-60)_2$, and $(-50/+40)_2$, respectively.

Effect of the number of layers on the structural behaviour of the wrapped concrete columns

a) Tissues reinforcement

The structural behaviour of the columns presented in Figure 4 is related to the concrete control specimens and the concrete columns wrapped by FRP bidirectional E-glass fibre tissue. The surface density of the FRP is 300 g/m^2 with a polyester resin for the lay-up $(0/90)_2$ and number of layers varying from one to four subjected, to compression loading until failure. The load history of the columns wrapped by FRP proceeds in three phases, similarly to Figure 2. Furthermore, the third phase is only observed when the concrete columns are wrapped by four layers - the case corresponding to the highest rigidity and the maximum load at failure.

Figure 4 Load/time curves of the concrete control compared to the columns wrapped by bidirectional tissue of surface density 300 g/m^2 with a number of turn varying from one to four.

Consequently, the improvement of the ultimate resistance of the columns wrapped by three and four turns is definitely higher than the one offered by specimens reinforced by one or two wraps. In other words, the number of turns plays a significant role on the repair and rehabilitation of the structures, and the increase in number of turns leads to the enhancement of the rigidity and strength.

Damage types of columns wrapped by tissue/polyester

Figure 5 show various cracking modes of the concrete control columns subjected to compression loading, as well as the columns wrapped by FRP with turns varying from 1 to 4. The failure of the concrete control columns is initiated by cracks which are formed under the higher support and which this develops with the increase in the load until the failure by shearing of the concrete. For the wrapped concrete columns a delamination is created between the strands of the vertical fibres and the horizontal one under the effect of the compression load by fibre buckling. The development of this delamination creates the cracks of the external layer of the composite jacket, which is then propagated thereafter and penetrated in the internal layer of the composites until the rupture of the vertical fibres.

Figure 5 Various damage modes. a) and b) control columns, c) to g) concrete columns wrapped by 1, 2, 3 and 4 turns respectively. h) delamination between the composite jacket and the concrete column.

In addition, the failure of the concrete inside the composite jacket causes an internal pressure under the expansion of concrete were a crack of horizontal fibres is formed and propagated vertically until the failure (scratch) of the composite jacket causing the final ruin of the specimen. The change of the colour of the specimen is due to the delamination between the composite jacket and the concrete column.

b) Mat reinforcement

The time history of the concrete columns load wrapped by Mat/polyester employing 1 to 4 layers presented in Figure 6 is similar to the one shown in Figure 4. An improvement on the strength is reported in particular for the concrete columns wrapped by four turns. However, this improvement of the strength is lower than that obtained in the case of wrapped concrete columns by a tissue having the same surface density of 300 g/m^2 .

Figure 6 Load/time curves of the columns wrapped by mat with surface density of 300 g/m^2 and polyester resin.

Damage types of columns wrapped by mat/polyester

Figure 7 represents the failure types of the columns wrapped by composite jacket with one to four turns of mat/polyester, the failure type is the same one for all the columns, however the structure becomes more fragile with the increase of the composite layers. The damage starts with the fall down of the concrete and with increasing load one obtains the delamination between the composite jacket and the concrete columns. As the mat is made by random oriented short fibres, the crack penetrates easily in the FRP jacket and the development of the delamination leads to the failure of the fibres. Finally, a vertical crack east creates the failure of the fibres under the expansion of concrete effect, while the failure of the specimens is obtained by the development of this crack.

Figure 7 Damage types the mat/polyester wrapped concrete columns with the number of turn varying from one to four layers.

c) Hybrid reinforcement

Figure 8 shows the load time history of the columns wrapped by mat/tissue/polyester and tissue/mat/polyester by employing one or two turn of each fibre type, compared to the concrete control sample. For the first type (tissue on the external part) the behaviour is very close to the mat/polyester wrapped concrete columns behaviour (Figure 6). The second type (mat on the external part) shows a similar behaviour to the one obtained for the tissue/polyester wrapped concrete columns (Figure 4). It can be concluded that in the hybrid case the best behaviour is obtained when the mat is on the external part (Figure 8b) on the load at failure is greater with 100 kN compared to the mat/tissue/polyester in the case of employing 2 turns of each fibre type reinforcement.

Figure 8 Load/time of hybrid wrapped concrete columns mat/tissue, and tissue/mat respectively.

Damage types of the hybrid wrapped concrete columns

From Figure 9, one can notice that the damage modes follow the load time history i.e. the damage of wrapped mat/tissue columns is similar to that obtained for the wrapped tissue/polyester (Figure 5), on the other hand the damage mode of mat/tissue/polyester is similar to the mat/polyester (Figure 7).

Figure 9 Failure modes of hybrid wrapped concrete columns mat/tissue, and tissue/mat respectively.

CONCLUSION

The reinforcement by composite materials can bring significant benefits to the structures for repair and rehabilitation. The composite can compensate for the stiffness loss of the columns due to the cracking of the concrete in compression, and increase the bearing capacity of the columns by exploiting good resistance during the concrete compression. The composite can also limit the excessive opening of the cracks and makes the structure less fragile, possibly changing the failure mode of the structure. The study of the reinforcement of the columns wrapped by FRP under uniaxial compression loading lead to the following conclusions:

- The fibre orientations and the thickness of the wall of the FRP wrapping have a considerable effect on the load time history, strength, ductility, and the damage modes of the composite concrete columns. The FRP reinforcement effect cannot be completely carried out without appropriate fibre orientation and sufficient wall thickness.
- The results obtained (in particular the maximum load for the FRP wrapped concrete columns) show the importance of using this technique. The worst case scenario is represented by an increase of ~ 51% of the maximum load for the lay-up (+ 50/-40)₂ where the load passes from 537.8 kN for the control (reference) columns to 815 kN for the wrapped ones. The best laminate stacking is (+ 30/-60)₂ where the load at failure reaches 910.5 kN, corresponding to an increase of 70% compared to the reference concrete columns.

- The knowledge of the damage types makes it possible to determine the most dangerous zones (more damaged) in order to reinforce them well. The damage strongly depends on the fibre orientations composite wrapped jacket.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The head of laboratory of Civil Engineering and Hydraulics (LGCH) of university of Guelma Pr. Guenfoud M. is acknowledges for the test carried out on his laboratory.

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